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Variety	Frequency distribution of yield in t/ha						Mean yield (t/ha)
	<1.0	<1.5	<2.0	<2.5	<3.0	>3.0	
CR231-1	1	3	3	0	2	1	1.9
Dular	2	1	1	2	2	1	2.1
IET7255	2	2	2	0	2	1	1.8
IET7259	2	1	2	2	0	2	2.0
IR50	1	1	5	0	0	2	1.8
IR9209-47-1-1-6-2	2	1	3	2	0	1	1.7
IR9729-67-3	2	0	2	2	1	2	2.2
IR9708-51-1-2	1	3	1	4	0	0	1.8
IR8608-189-2-2-1-3	2	1	3	1	1	1	1.7
IR13204-24-1-6	1	3	2	2	1	0	1.7
Kiran	1	3	2	1	0	2	2.1
Panke	1	1	5	0	0	2	2.0
Suweon 287	1	2	3	1	1	1	1.8
Mean							2.0
CD at 5%							0.2

reproductive phases. Panke, an indigenous genotype, yielded an average 1.9 t/ha (see table).

In 1983, the environmental conditions were more favorable. BG367-7 yielded highest, 2.5 t/ha followed by BKNLR-75091 and BG367-4 (see table). Of the varieties tested, Panke, Kiran, and IET7259 had the most stable yields. □

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Genetic Evaluation and Utilization HYBRID RICE

Evaluation of F₁ hybrids on the Cuu Long Delta, Vietnam

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We evaluated six F₁ hybrids developed at CLRRI in 1984 dry season in a randomized block design with three replications. There were eight 4-m-long rows per plot. Plants were transplanted at 20 × 15-cm spacing, and received 75-26-25 kg NPK/ha.

The F₁ hybrids had negative heterobeltiosis in plant height, panicles/m²,

Table 2. Performance of F₁ hybrids in Oman, Hau Giang, Vietnam, 1984 dry season.

Hybrid and check varieties	Duration (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Pan/m ²	Grains /pan	Sterility (%)	1000-g wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)
V20A/NN3A (IR36)	93	69	265	76	20.3	31	4.0
Zhen Shan 97 A /NN3A	93	78	263	86	23.2	28	4.9
NN3A	105	90	412	101	17.9	23	5.6
V20A/NN4B (IR42)	97	83	276	77	19.6	30	6.5
Zhen Shan 97 A /NN4B	97	76	277	121	11.5	27	5.6
NN4B	135	86	375	107	16.6	22	4.8
V20A/IR54	95	75	299	79	20.9	31	2.5
Zhen Shan 97 A /IR54	95	76	291	89	22.8	29	2.9
IR54	122	91	361	112	15.8	26	6.0
V20B	97	71	284	74	16.5	30	2.3
97B	103	74	269	97	26.1	28	2.8
CV%		9	17	14	24		15
LSD 5%		10	72	19	6.6		1.1

Table 1. Standard heterosis and heterobeltiosis in yield of F₁ hybrids, Omon, Vietnam, 1984.

Hybrid	Standard heterosis (compared with NN3A)	Heterobeltiosis
V20A/NN4B	+16.45	+33.19
Zhen Shan 97A/NN4B	+0.54	+17.57
Zhen Shan 97A/NN3A	-12.53	-12.53
V20A/NN3A	-33.39	-33.39
Zhen Shan 97A/IR54	-51.75	-51.99
V20A/IR54	-55.81	-58.97

grains/panicle, and sterility and positive heterobeltiosis in 1,000-grain weight (Table 1).

Only V20A/NN4B and Zhen Shan 97A/NN4B performed better than the best parents. They yielded 6.5 and 5.6 t/ha (Table 2). These hybrids had positive standard yield heterosis and heterobeltiosis (Table 1) compared with commercial NN3A. V20A/NN4B and Zhen Shan 97A/NN4B yielded 46% more. Other hybrids did not yield well. Generally, the F₁ hybrids yielded poorly because of a genetic defect in cytoplasmic male

sterile (cms) lines used.

NN4B was a better restorer than NN3A and IR54 for the cms lines V20A and Zhen Shan 97A in Vietnam. □

Harvest index and straw weight of some experimental F₁ rice hybrids

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Crop grain yield is the product of harvest index (HI) and total dry matter. Theore-